

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

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Report on current screening and enforcement structures

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OF
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FROM
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Responsible author(s)	Tonie Wickman/RISE/tonie.wickman@ri.se
Co-authors	Nina Melander/RISE/nina.melander@ri.se Petteri Talasniemi/Tukes/petteri.talasniemi@tukes.fi Karin Rumar/KEMI/karin.rumar@kemi.se Chijioke Olisah/MU/chijioke.olisah@recetox.muni.cz Lisa Melymuk/MU/lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz Robin Vestergren/KEMI/robin.vestergren@kemi.se Urban Boije af Gennäs/KEMI/urban.boijeafgennas@kemi.se Sicco Brandsma/VUA/sicco.brandsma@vu.nl Martin Scheringer/MU/martin.scheringer@recetox.muni.cz
Internal Reviewers ²	Lina Wendt-Rasch, Kemi, (WP6 lead)
External Reviewers ³	The Forum for Exchange of Information on Enforcement / ECHA / forum@echa.europa.eu
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Abstract

This report aims to provide valuable insights into the current enforcement practices, methods, challenges, and prospects in the European Union. The coverage of enforcement included in this study was chemicals in articles, complex objects, and chemical products as defined in REACH Regulation, POP Regulation, RoHS Directive, Toys directive, and CLP Regulation. The report offers recommendations for improving enforcement practices based on a questionnaire and interviews with professionals from multiple EEA states.

The recommended future areas of focus intend to present some activities that are of particularly high value for improving enforcement in the EEA. The identified four areas were 1) development of analytical testing methods, 2) development of tools to improve enforcement, 3) co-operation and networks within the framework of the ECHA Forum, and 4) enforcement of online sales and imported products.

One of the important aspects of the enforceability of regulatory measures restricting the use of certain hazardous substances is the availability of analytical methods that ensure a proper assessment of the presence of substances in products. Harmonized and standardized analytical methods do not exist for all substances under the scope of chemical legislation. It is important to support the development of testing methods. The absence of methods hampers a harmonized control of conformity of products. In addition, it is important to ensure that there is sufficient laboratory capacity for analyzing substances within Europe. To enhance laboratory capacity, promoting the designation of European Union Testing Facilities (EUTFs) under the Market Surveillance Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 is recommended.

It is important to continue developing IT tools, AI-based systems, and other tools to facilitate market surveillance authorities in selecting products for enforcement. Examples of such tools include web crawlers designed to facilitate the finding of non-compliant products on online shops. In general, the digitalization of information, such as electronic safety data sheets and digital product passports, along with various databases, can facilitate the better transfer of chemical information within the supply chain.

The ECHA Forum plays a pivotal role in coordinating and harmonizing various EU-wide enforcement activities. It is important to enhance co-operation and networks within the framework of the ECHA Forum. EEA-wide enforcement projects have a significant role in ensuring the compliance of products within the EEA market.

Online sales have gained significant popularity in recent years, particularly during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. ECHA Forum projects have shown that online sale of chemicals is an area of high non-compliance. EEA cooperation is particularly important for learning together how the enforcement of online sales can be carried out. It is important to organize awareness campaigns and other ways to increase the level of knowledge regarding the legal obligations when selling products online. Customs plays a significant role at the EEA borders in ensuring that products entering the EEA market comply with regulations. Market surveillance authorities need to continue enhancing the cooperation with customs authorities.

This work was performed as part of the Horizon HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVLTH-03 project PARC – Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals, which is an EU-wide research and innovation partnership program to support EU and national chemical risk assessment and risk management bodies with new data, knowledge, methods, networks, and skills to address current, emerging and novel chemical safety challenges (Marx-Stoelting et.al. 2023).

Key words

Market surveillance, enforcement, chemical legislation, chemical products; articles; digital product passport, analytical methods; online sales; border control, resources.

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Acronyms

AdCos	Administrative Cooperation Groups
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BPR	Biocidal Product Regulations
CE	Conformite Europeenne
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, or toxic for Reproduction
DSA	Digital Services Act
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEA	European Economic Area
EU	European Union
EUPCN	EU Product Compliance Network
EUTFs	European Union Testing Facilities
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
GPSD	General Product Safety Directive
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
ICSMS	Information and Communication System for Market Surveillance
KemI	Swedish Chemicals Agency
LC-QTOF/MS	Liquid chromatography quadrupole time of flight mass spectrometry
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PIC	Prior Informed Consent
POPs	Persistent Organic Pollutants
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
RAC	Committee for Risk Assessment
RAPEX	The Rapid Exchange of Information System
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
REF	REACH-EN-FORCE
RoHS	Restriction of Hazardous Substances
SCCP	Short Chain Chlorinated Paraffins
SCIP	Substances of Concern In articles as such or in complex objects (Products)
SDS	Safety Data Sheets
SEAC	Committee for Socio-economic Analysis
SVHC	Substances of Very High Concern
TUKES	Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency
VOC	Volatile Organic Compound
XRF	X-ray Fluorescence

Glossary

Article

An object which during production is given a special shape, surface or design which determines its function to a greater degree than does its chemical composition. (EU, 2006)

Chemical product

Refers to a chemical substance or mixture according to the REACH Regulation (EU 2006) identified by a manufacturer and trade name. For chemical products the chemical composition defines its function more than shape, surface, or design. (cleaning products, cosmetics, and biocides, for example).

Complex object

An object made up of more than one article. (ECHA, 2017a)

Material

A non-specific and non-legal term to describe for example: plastic, rubber, metal, textile, wood, paper

Product

A non-specific and non-legal term to broadly describe substances, mixtures, materials or articles that are provided on the EU market by a manufacturer under a trade name.

Substance

A chemical element and its compounds in the natural state or obtained by any manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity deriving from the process used, but excluding any solvent which may be separated without affecting the stability of the substance or changing its composition. (EU, 2006).

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of this study

This project aimed to identify gaps and needs in the enforcement of chemicals in products for market surveillance, to give a background for further development of tools and methodologies that could support market surveillance authorities. Given the anticipated rollout of numerous policies and reforms in the 2020s, enforcers will encounter novel challenges and demands. The coverage of enforcement included in this study were chemicals in articles, complex objects, and chemical products as defined in REACH Regulation (*see glossary*), POPs Regulation, RoHS Directive, Toys directive, and CLP Regulation.

Enhancing chemical enforcement contributes to achieving regulatory compliance, safeguarding the safety and wellbeing of citizens and workers by minimizing risks associated with chemical exposure, and mitigating the adverse ecological impact of hazardous substances. It plays a crucial role in upholding the EU's reputation as a standard-bearer for responsible chemical management. Moreover, chemical enforcement catalyzes innovation by incentivizing the development of safer alternatives, fostering responsible chemical practices across industries, and establishing a level playing field for companies. In a broader context, enforcement forms the backbone of the EU's overarching commitment to sustainability, pollution reduction, and ensuring fair competition throughout the industry and supply chain.

1.2. Enforcement in EU and EEA today

The purpose of the market surveillance carried out by the authorities is to ensure compliance of products with regulations and that no dangerous or unsafe products are for sale in the EU. Fulfilling legislation on chemicals is a requirement for companies producing, importing, and trading products within the EU. Market surveillance authorities typically do not carry out advance inspections or grant approvals for products before they are placed on the market. Instead, they control products on the market, including through online stores. Authorities conduct spot-checks on only a fraction of products, as the number of products produced and imported on the market far exceeds the enforcement capacity. To ensure effective surveillance amidst numerous regulations, cooperation, coordination, and information exchange are vital among enforcement and customs authorities in EEA states.

European cooperation on market surveillance takes place through the EU Product Compliance Network (EUPCN) established by the Market Surveillance Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, and in cooperation groups of market surveillance authorities known as Administrative Cooperation Groups (AdCos). The aim of these networks is to facilitate cooperation by coordinating activities, exchanging information, developing and implementing joint enforcement projects, and exchanging expertise and best practices in market surveillance. To facilitate the necessary cooperation within the chemical sector, the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) established a body called "The Forum for Exchange of Information on Enforcement" which is referred to as "The ECHA Forum" in this report. The ECHA Forum plays a pivotal role in coordinating EU-wide enforcement activities. While enforcement activities can only cover a small number of products and articles on the market, previous enforcement activities show that breaches of chemical legislation on the European market are an extensive problem. In 2023, the ECHA Forum published the results of the EU-wide enforcement project REF-10. The report shows that excessive levels of hazardous chemicals, such as lead and phthalates, were found in products sold to consumers (ECHA, 2023). In total, 18% of the 2,400 inspected products in 26 countries, mostly intended for consumers, breached EU chemicals laws. This included electrical devices (52% non-compliant), sports equipment (18% non-compliant), toys (23% non-compliant), and fashion products (15% non-compliant).

EEA states are obliged to establish necessary national arrangements for effective enforcement. However, each EEA state decides how enforcement is conducted, and it can be divided between different national authorities, regulatory bodies, or relevant governmental agencies depending on legislation. A common arrangement in EEA states is to separate the legislative body, responsible for developing new legislation, from the department conducting enforcement, as these are separate activities. Promoting compliance, such as through national REACH/CLP/BPR Helpdesks, aims to support companies and enhance awareness of legal obligations among stakeholders. This task is distinct from the role of the enforcing authority but is crucial, as relying solely on

enforcement is often not enough. The authorities involved in enforcement can typically be, for example, health and safety inspectorates, environmental inspectorates, consumer protection, agriculture, food, and customs authorities. In most countries, these responsibilities can be further divided among national, regional, and/or local levels according to their respective jurisdictions.

Regardless of how responsibility is distributed within a country, the Market Surveillance Regulation requires EEA states to draw up an overarching national market surveillance strategy which will promote a consistent, comprehensive, and integrated approach to market surveillance and to the enforcement of EU legislation within the territory of the EEA state (e.g. Finland, 2022). In addition to the requirements, the ECHA Forum recommends that countries develop a national strategy for chemical enforcement, including assessing, securing, and promoting compliance with regulations (ECHA, 2017b). The strategy may include activities for routine (proactive) or non-routine (reactive) work. Each strategy should set out clear policy objectives and priorities, suitable organizational provision, actual enforcement measures, procedures for monitoring and measurement and review, and evaluation and updating of enforcement strategy, based on the monitoring procedures (e.g. Estonia, 2022).

1.3. Overview of the enforcement process

For day-to-day work, enforcement professionals generally follow a common surveillance process as seen in Figure 1 and described below.

- 1. Choosing a product on the market:** Proactive enforcement is mainly conducted through local, national, or EU-wide projects. To ensure relevant products are surveilled, professionals may employ a risk-based approach to identify and prioritize products based on potential health and environmental impact and compliance history. National product registers can also be used to prioritize chemical products. Surveillance activities can be initiated before certain issues arise to prevent violations or as a response to complaints or incidents for specific products. Products can also be chosen to target specific sectors, industries, or products. Reactive enforcement can be triggered by reports from consumers, industry, and other authorities or notifications from Safety Gate (European Commission 2024).
- 1. Product checks and tests:** Authorities can carry out product checks in different ways, for example, by checking the labels, examining information found on websites, purchasing or requesting product samples, and conducting chemical analyses. Surveillance may include examining product labels to ensure accurate and compliant information provided to consumers and reviewing documentation like registration records, Declaration of conformity or Safety Data Sheets to verify legal compliance. To assess the composition of products, laboratory tests can be conducted to test for specific regulated chemicals, especially for articles and mixtures.
- 2. Reports and measures:** Feedback is provided to the responsible economic operator (manufacturer, importer, etc.) to gather information and address compliance issues, enforce corrective action, both mandatory and voluntary, to rectify non-compliance and mitigate potential harm.
- 3. Follow-up surveillance and announcements:** To ensure that the economic operator has implemented the correct measures in response to the identified issue, any non-compliance is followed up. Further announcements at both national and EEA levels can be made to inform the public, industry stakeholders, and other relevant authorities (e.g. Safety Gate). This contributes to transparency and encourages compliance across borders.

Figure 1 General overview of the surveillance process (Finland's national market surveillance strategy, 2022-2025)

1.4. Measures and actions

When finding a non-compliant product, enforcement authorities can consider various factors to determine the most appropriate course of action. These considerations are used to guide authorities, enabling them to make well-informed decisions, and ensuring a targeted and effective response to regulatory breaches in chemical legislation. Factors taken into consideration may include the degree of non-compliance, hazards and risks posed to humans and the environment by substances, mixtures, or articles, as well as the quantity information (e.g. tonnage, number of articles) related to their manufacturing, importing, and supply.

The size of duty holders' positions and influence in the supply chain can also impact the measures and actions taken, along with their compliance history. This can also include an examination of the duty holder's actions, assessing whether reasonable precautions and due diligence were taken. Additionally, the presence of intent behind non-compliance, differentiating between deliberate actions for commercial gain and potential competitive advantage from not complying may also be a factor. Further considerations encompass the duty holder's adherence to general conditions, their attitudes, and the level of cooperation displayed during the enforcement process. Collectively, these factors contribute to a comprehensive assessment that guides enforcement authorities in determining an effective and targeted response to instances of non-compliance. Decisions following non-compliance are made on a case-by-case basis, guided by legal requirements and the enforcement authority's policies. The options for enforcement include verbal/written advice, withdrawal of the product from the market, a ban on sales, product recalls and public announcements. In addition to enforcement measures, sanctions can also be imposed for the non-compliant products (e.g. fines, criminal complaint / handing over to public prosecutor's office, police). The EEA states are mandated to establish penalty frameworks that impose effective, proportionate, and dissuasive penalties for non-compliance, but it is up to each EEA state how to implement the framework. National legislation can differ when it comes to possibilities for some enforcement actions like reporting to the police/prosecutor, fines, injunctions etc.

1.5. European chemicals legislation

There are two major types of EU chemical legislation: regulations, and directives. Regulations automatically form part of the chemical's regulation in each EU state and in the EEA, which means they are also binding for Norway, Iceland, and Lichtenstein. Directives are legislative acts that the individual EEA states need to develop into national laws. In addition, there are several global conventions for countries that have ratified them. For example, the Stockholm Convention regulating persistent organic pollutants (POPs) is implemented in EEA countries through the POP Regulation (EU) No 2019/1021.

Chemical legislation considered in this report were:

REACH Regulation ((EC) No 1907/2006)

The REACH Regulation stands for Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals. The REACH Regulation covers requirements for chemical products and articles. In principle, it applies to all chemical substances; not only those used in industrial processes but also in our day-to-day lives, for example in cleaning products and paints, as well as in articles such as clothes, furniture and electrical appliances. Annex XVII of the REACH Regulation sets out restrictions for certain substances known to pose risks to both humans and the environment. Among other things, the REACH Regulation contains obligations linked to substances of very high concern (SVHC) included in the so-called Candidate List.

CLP Regulation ((EU) No 2019/1021)

The CLP Regulation on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures requires manufacturers, importers or downstream users of substances or mixtures to classify, label and package their hazardous chemicals appropriately before placing them on the market. CLP sets detailed criteria for the hazard classification and labelling elements. Hazard labelling allows the hazard classification to be communicated to the user of a substance or mixture through labels and safety data sheets. CLP is also the basis for many other legislative provisions on risk management of chemicals.

POPs regulation (EU No 2019/1021)

The Regulation on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) prohibits the placing on the market and use of several substances that are persistent and that can harm humans and the environment. Like the REACH, the POP Regulation essentially applies to all chemical mixtures and articles.

RoHS directive (EU/2011/65)

RoHS stands for Restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment. The RoHS Directive is a product-specific directive for electrical and electronic equipment that restricts the use of certain metals, flame retardants and phthalates. Among other things, the directive requires products to be labelled. The CE mark indicates that the manufacturer certifies that the requirements of specific EU legislation are met, and the contact details indicate which companies are responsible for the product.

Toy Safety Directive (2009/48/EC)

The EU Toy Safety Directive contains several requirements for the chemical content of toys, including limit values for how much of certain metals may be released, restrictions on the content of CMR substances (substances that can cause cancer, genetic mutations or damage to the reproductive system) and perfume substances. As in the RoHS Directive, the Toy Safety Directive contains labelling requirements.

There are several additional legislations regulating chemicals at the EU level for specific product groups or substances (like detergents, VOC, batteries, F-gases, cosmetics, food contact materials, biocides, etc.) that are not covered by the scope of this report.

1.6. Other regulations and tools important for chemical enforcement

The European Market Surveillance Regulation establishes a uniform framework for market surveillance of products at EEA level. It complements and strengthens existing provisions in chemical legislation relating to the ensuring of compliance of products and enforcement. It aims to prevent consumers and workers from risks associated with non-compliant products. The regulation is intended to protect against harmful products, where exposure to hazardous chemicals is just one safety aspect of many. There may be different authorities or ministries responsible for chemical enforcement and national market surveillance. For example, in Sweden, there are 16 other market surveillance authorities with 42 different areas of responsibilities, adding to the Swedish Chemicals Agency. Examples of such authorities are the Swedish Transport Agency for non-road mobile machinery, the Medical Products Agency for tattoo inks, and the Swedish Board of Agriculture for fertilizing products.

There are also horizontal legislations where all market surveillance authorities are responsible for consumer products: the General Product Safety Directive 2001/95/EC (GPSD) and the updated General Product Safety Regulation (EU) 2023/988 (GPSR). Another example of horizontal legislation is the Digital Services Act (EU) 2022/2065 (DSA) which regulates the obligations of digital services, including marketplaces, that act as intermediaries in their role of connecting consumers with goods, services, and content. Its main goal is to prevent illegal and harmful activities online and the spread of disinformation. DSA is an important regulation from the perspective of enforcement of online sales.

The EU rapid alert system for dangerous non-food products (Safety Gate, earlier RAPEX) enables information to be circulated quickly among the national authorities responsible for product safety in the EEA states. Every day, national authorities send alerts to the Safety Gate. Each alert contains information on the kind of product detected as dangerous, a description of the risk and the measures taken by the economic operator or ordered

by the authority. Every alert is followed up by authorities in other countries, which take their own measures if they find the same product on their own national markets. The European Commission publishes an overview report about the dangerous products that have been notified by the EEA States on its Safety Gate internet portal every week. Related to the European Market Surveillance Regulation, there is a database “The Information and communication system for market surveillance” (ICSMS) which is a common platform used by market surveillance authorities in different countries to share their product investigations, inform each other about their results and the measures taken. The objective of the database is to check if the same products have been investigated by another country, and to get statistics from enforcement. The non-compliant cases can from ICSMS be inserted directly into the Safety Gate, which means that they are closely linked.

There are a few national regulations that require chemicals enforcement, but as these are generally small additions they are not included in this report. The main national differences are related to sanctions and fees, penalties for non-compliance, as described above.

1.7. The ECHA Forum

The Forum for Exchange of Information on Enforcement (Forum) is a network of authorities responsible for the enforcement of a number of European Regulations on chemicals (REACH, CLP, PIC, POP and Biocidal Product regulations) in the EU, Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein. The Forum is established under the REACH Regulation and is a body of ECHA. The Forum is composed of members appointed by the EEA States.

The ECHA Forum aims to contribute to harmonized enforcement of chemical regulations. Among other tasks, the Forum is mandated to identify best practices in enforcement and develop tools of use to local inspectors. This Forum and the Biocidal Products Regulation Subgroup run several working groups to manage its tasks. They also give advice and support to ECHA’s Committees (RAC and SEAC) on the enforceability of new REACH restriction proposals. The Forum has developed a methodology and a living document containing recommended analytical methods as a guide for local inspectors to check compliance with Annex XVII restrictions under REACH (ECHA, 2016).

The ECHA Forum coordinates various enforcement projects, one of the main ones being the REACH-EN-FORCE (REF) projects which are designed to harmonize enforcement in each EEA state and check the current level of compliance (ECHA, 2010). A working group within the ECHA Forum prioritizes and proposes annually the subject for the next harmonized enforcement project from proposals for REF projects submitted by Forum members, the ECHA Secretariat, the Commission and the Stakeholder Organizations accredited by ECHA (ASOs). The REF projects are carried out by inspectors based at the national authorities in the participating EEA states. Besides the REF projects, the Forum undertakes smaller-scale pilot projects. The Forum also prepares the project manual (guidance document, checklist, planning, recommendations) and arranges training events focused on the needs of the inspectors for the execution of the project. For example, the upcoming REF-13 project will focus on enforcing products sold online. Inspections for this REF-13 project will take place in 2025. The objective is to check that products sold online, such as toys, common household goods or chemicals, comply with REACH restrictions. Inspectors will also check that mixtures are classified, labelled and packaged in line with CLP and that online offers include the required information about the hazards of mixtures. Inspectors may also check compliance with restrictions under the Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) Regulation and the Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS) Directive. Other examples of enforcement projects are presented in Table 1.

Reports from enforcement activities and other documents related to the Forum work are openly available on ECHA's website ([Forum enforcement projects - ECHA \(europa.eu\)](#)).

Table 1 Examples of ECHA Forum enforcement projects

REF-8: Enforcement of CLP, REACH and BPR duties related to substances, mixtures and articles sold on-line	2019-2021
REF-9: Enforcement of authorization	2020-2023
REF-10: Integrated chemical control of products	2021-2024
REF-11: Enforcement of safety data sheets (SDS)	2022-2025
Pilot project: Enforcement of restrictions of PFCAs and related substances focusing on cosmetics	2023-2025
REF-12: Enforcement of imported substances, mixtures, and articles	2023-2026
REF-13: Enforcement of products sold online	2024-2027

2. Methodology

2.1. A two-steps approach

This study was made in two steps. First, we developed a questionnaire, distributed by e-mail, to gather information and then we performed interviews. In both cases, the questions were developed in collaboration with PARC partners involved in chemicals enforcement at national levels. In this study we employed an exploratory and descriptive qualitative approach for data collection. We focused on chemicals enforcement, but the national structures differ in how enforcement responsibilities are divided among different national authorities and thereby different authorities or ministries were involved. The amount of collaboration between different agencies in each country also differs.

2.2. Questionnaire distribution

In spring 2023, a questionnaire was circulated to relevant authorities in Europe to understand databases used by practitioners and methods used in enforcement activities, including questions about the type of information, criteria, and analytical methods used by these agencies in enforcement activities. Additionally, it addressed the challenges encountered in enforcing chemicals in articles and chemical products. The outcomes of the latter sections of the survey are detailed in the present report.

The questionnaire was distributed to 215 recipients from a European Commission list of authorities responsible for conducting chemical management and enforcement activities (European Commission 2024). The survey yielded 18 responses, of which 14 indicated that their agency was responsible for enforcement activities concerning chemical products or articles. The number of responses was low but similar questions were used for the interviews, partly performed with people from other countries and authorities, therefore a combination gives a more reliable result. Countries represented are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Venn diagram showing countries where interview and survey responses were obtained.

Figure 3. Map of Europe showing the countries (highlighted in blue) where interview and survey responses were obtained from (*plotted on mapchart.net*).

2.3. Interview procedure and selecting professionals

In addition to the questionnaire, data collection was performed through interviews conducted with inspectors from enforcement agencies affiliated with the ECHA Forum, in the autumn of 2023. The individuals contacted for interviews were distinct from those who responded to the questionnaire survey, as different contact lists were used. The chance to get a higher response rate was one reason for changing the contact list compared to that used for the questionnaire. Members of the ECHA Forum are practitioners in chemicals enforcement. Every designated contact person on the ECHA Forum's list was approached via email with a request for an interview. The interviews were conducted online for about 1-2 hours with individuals or groups of up to 5 people. Notes, video recordings and transcripts were documented.

The direct contact for interviews with the ECHA Forum resulted in representatives from 12 countries agreeing to participate in the interviews. Conversely, representatives from 14 countries either indicated unavailability or did not respond. The 12 EEA countries represented are shown in Figure 2. It is worth noting the absence of several of the largest economies in the EU such as Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, and Austria, which may affect the outcome. Interviews were conducted with enforcement specialists often responsible for specific legislations such as REACH, CLP, POP or RoHS. In a few cases, the interviewed enforcement specialists were mainly focusing on industrial production, occupational health or pesticide use in farming/food production and lacked own experiences on enforcing the type of products that were the focus of this study.

2.4. Interview questions

The interviews aimed to gain further insight into the current methodologies, challenges, desired solutions, and positive experiences of enforcement agencies. Five open-ended interview questions were formulated for this purpose and sent beforehand to respective agencies and contact persons:

Questions to enforcement professionals

- a. *Can you describe the methods and approaches your organization employs for chemical enforcement, including testing and monitoring processes?*
- b. *How do you prioritize chemicals or articles for testing and regulation? Are there specific criteria or risk assessment models you rely on?*
- c. *In your experience, what are the most significant challenges you face in enforcing chemical regulations, and what strategies have been effective in overcoming these challenges?*
- d. *Looking ahead, what tools or technologies do you believe would significantly enhance the effectiveness of chemical enforcement efforts in the future?*
- e. *Could you share examples of successful cases where chemical substitution or regulatory actions have had a positive impact on public and environmental health?*

To ensure the clarity and relevance of the interview questions, pilot tests were conducted with the Swedish Chemical Agency (KemI) and Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes). This pre-testing phase aimed to refine questions, ensuring the comprehensibility and capability of pertinent responses. The data collection process followed an inductive approach where probing follow-up questions were used as necessary. Probing involved both clarifications, aimed at addressing vague responses, and expansion, encouraging participants to provide more detailed insights into specific topics.

Thematic analysis was used to identify recurring patterns and themes brought up during interviews for respective questions.

3. Results and discussion

The results reflect a synthesis of the responses to the questionnaires and interviews highlighting the major themes defined by the questions posed.

3.1. Methods for enforcement

In the interviews we asked for methods and approaches the organizations employed for chemical enforcement, including testing and monitoring processes. Answers to this section have been integrated in the introduction section, or below in the results and discussion section, under relevant headings, to avoid repetition.

3.2 Methods for prioritization

To prioritize, different kinds of information, criteria, methods and tools are used. This could be seen from the questionnaire result (Figure 4), and it was also seen in the interviews, adding to what was described in the section “Overview of the enforcement process”.

Figure 4: Questionnaire responses from agencies from 14 countries related to the following question on enforcement activities in Europe. *Please choose which option best describes the criteria, methods and tools used when prioritizing Articles/ Chemical Products for inspections in enforcement?*

Strategies for prioritizing chemicals and articles includes the utilization of risk assessment approaches and prioritization based on articles affecting vulnerable groups, such as children and the elderly. Also, the frequency of checks can depend on risk assessment – in one country high risk meant checks every year, medium risk every two years and low risk maybe check once every three years. In another country they try to each year enforce something not earlier enforced, otherwise choose those that are judged as high risk-level and high probability for non-compliance. An illustration of a risk matrix used in Finland is seen in Figure 5.

Theoretical Hazard or Risk			
Probability / exposure	Minor effects Unclassified chemicals	Adverse effects Classified chemicals (except serious effects). Substances where precaution principles can be applied.	Serious effects CMR-, PBT- substances, sensitizing substances, other SVHC-substances. Acute toxic and corrosive substances
Unlikely No significant use in Finland. Non dispersive use, no consumer use.	Negligible Odor or comfort "harm". No clear symptoms or effects. Measure: take note	Minor Clear but reversiblesymptoms /effects. (skin, CNS, eye) Measure: issuing guidance, advice	Moderate Symptoms that need medical care, environment or ground water damage Measure: prohibition of sale / distribution, Safety Gate
Possible Professional use in Finland. Small scale consumer use. Local scale environmental releases.	Minor Odor or comfort "harm". No clear symptoms or effects. Measure: take note + follow up	Moderate Clear but reversiblesymptoms /effects. (skin, CNS, eye) Measure: "hearing" (+ other enforcement measures)	Significant Symptoms that need medical care, environment or ground water damage. Measure: prohibition of sale / distribution, Safety Gate
Probable Wide dispersive use, large scale professional or consumer use. Exposure of children possible	Minor Odor or comfort "harm". No clear symptoms or effects. Measure: take note, follow up Issuing guidance	Significant Clear but reversiblesymptoms /effects. Measure: prohibition of sale / distribution, Safety Gate	Untolerable + CMR-effects, serious physical damage, Death, Wide environment or ground water damage Measure: market withdrawal / recall procedure, Safety Gate

Figure 5. Example of risk matrix for prioritizing chemical products, from Finland.

The use of notifications in Safety Gate serves as a valuable tool, especially in reactive enforcement, alerting authorities of potential risks. Another reactive enforcement technique mentioned by several interviewees was to base enforcement on complaints from citizens and institutions.

A common consideration is to focus on specific product groups, such as toys, clothing, construction, electronics, sport and leisure. Other ways mentioned to prioritize are to focus on cheap products or e-commerce, which both have shown a high rate of non-compliance, and trying to focus large volumes of articles and/or chemicals. Explorative detective work to identify emerging trends was also mentioned, especially concerning new and popular toys with a short market lifespan such as fidget spinners and squishies, as well as prioritizing new chemicals regulations. Prioritization on what to analyze may also depend on what chemical analysis can be provided by procured labs, the budget for analysis and the probability of finding non-compliant products.

Due to financial and practical constraints, and as the items normally have to be paid for, many enforcers are limited to smaller, cheaper articles and complex objects, hindering enforcement of larger, more expensive complex objects that may be of concern, such as furniture or motor vehicles. With a limited budget, it is more efficient to buy a larger amount of middle or lower-price range products than buying a few expensive items. Cheap items can sometimes be taken for free while more expensive products could not be justified/would not be fair to expect the companies to provide for free.

Some interviewees mentioned they buy products in shops, not announcing their cause. For e-commerce it is more common to pay for articles, and to do mystery shopping, not to announce being from inspectorates. Justifying taking samples for free is one reason to rather enforce higher levels in the supply chain, and not the local shop. Another reason is that higher levels may impact a larger part of the market, compared to the local shops.

With the exception of taking samples and performing chemical analysis, desktop inspections are very common, especially for chemical products where Substance Data Sheets (SDS) can be scrutinized. For chemical products, data from customs on chemicals import or statistics can also be used in planning for enforcement activities. The Nordic countries have national chemical product registers that are useful especially for prioritizing chemical products for enforcement.

These multifaceted strategies may also be impacted by the individual professional's experience and knowledge. Depending on the country's administrative structures, priorities can be set by the ministry, national administration and/or at a regional and/or municipal level.

3.3. Analytical methods

Analytical methods for screening and validation of compliance (or non-compliance) constitute a vital aspect of chemical enforcement, especially for articles. Of the 17 responses from the questionnaire, 18% indicated in-house XRF and contracted mass spectrometry as their primary tools for validating the chemical composition of products (Figure 6a). Additionally, 29% mentioned other specific techniques (not listed in the options) as their preferred tool, such as atomic spectroscopy, HPLC, and LC-QTOF/MS (Figure 6a). XRF also emerged as the predominant choice for screening (Figure 6b). In some interviews, XRF was mentioned to be used to indicate polymer type, as PVC contains chlorine, which is shown by XRF, and therefore a way to prioritize what additives to look for, using other suitable methods for validation of chemical composition.

Figures 6(a and b): Questionnaire responses from agencies from 14 countries related to the following questions on enforcement activities in Europe. (6a): *Which of the following analytical testing tool do you use for chemical analysis/validation of chemical composition of the products in enforcement activities?* (6b): *Which of the following analytical testing tool do you use for screening of chemical composition of the products in enforcement activities*

Except for XRF, which is common to have in-house, Raman and FTIR were other analytical methods used for screening, that some listed to have in-house. However, for most chemical analysis, contract laboratories are used, both according to the questionnaire and interviews. In some countries there are central national laboratories that can perform some analysis, but most need to purchase analysis from commercial labs, within the country or abroad. Commercial laboratories need to be procured, requiring public procurement rules to be followed. For regular analysis the authorities may have longer contracts. The in-house screening methods, like XRF, decrease the number of negative samples to be sent for more expensive analysis.

3.4. Information campaigns and helpdesks

Due to lack of awareness of chemical content and of chemicals legislation at companies, especially for importers and downstream users, helpdesks and information campaigns are a crucial part of the work of improving compliance. The best scenario for society is that companies know and want to comply with legislation, and that they do the best they can to avoid getting products which are not compliant, as one of the interviewees said. Several interviewees say they give advice rather than sanctions. Blame and shame might be efficient, but few enforcement authorities seem to use this tool. As a company, knowing what you have in your products and what chemicals regulations are relevant may present a daunting task. Helpdesks play an important role. But also, proactive communication with the industry was identified by several professionals as a crucial element in preparing for enforcement. Authorities strategically create a buzz within the sector, prompting a shift in the industry's approach to chemical management. One case exemplifying this led to several companies joining a national industry group for chemical management and substitution within the textile sector.

3.5. Challenges in enforcing chemical regulations

The enforcement of chemical regulations faces a myriad of challenges that span from the lack of material knowledge, analytical limitations, legislative complexities, technological gaps and economic constraints, including personnel shortages and costs related to sampling and analysis. From the questionnaire it is seen that insufficient analytical methods for chemicals in articles and chemical products (39%), online sales (18%) and border control (15%), are seen as the main challenges (Figure 7), and these were also seen as challenges in the interviews. Some of the most frequent challenges given in the interviews are further described below.

Figure 7. Responses to the questionnaire from agencies regarding the aspects considered most challenging on enforcement on chemical product or article regulations.

3.5.1 Chemical analysis

A lack of harmonized, verified or standardized chemical methods is a challenge several of the interviewees mentioned. Harmonized standardized methods for chemical analysis do exist but not for all substances under the scope of chemical legislation. Non-harmonized methods are used as a substitute in their place. This poses issues for enforcement when imposing legal consequences, as non-standardized methods may not be viewed as sufficient evidence of non-compliance in court. Future group restrictions, like for PFAS, face the absence of analytical methods, and a general lack of standardized analytical approaches. A lack of reference standards tailored to specific chemical groups is also a challenge. The restriction process should be linked with the development of new analytical methods. This issue is even more challenging with an increasing number of substances and chemical groups regulated.

Knowledge of what substances to analyze is often limited. The complexity of materials, several materials and components in complex objects, would justify the use of non-target screening approaches, but these are costly and therefore not routinely implemented. This challenge is paired with the challenge of identifying polymer types in various plastics. Plastics are known to contain a wide range of additives that can be associated with different polymer types. For example, in PVC it is common to find phthalates and SCCP, but in general it can be challenging to prioritize what to analyze in what material. A cheap, accessible and fast chemical method to identify polymer and a database telling what additives to expect would facilitate this work.

The availability of laboratories to perform certain chemical analyses varies between EEA states. In some countries there are very limited opportunities for contracting an accredited lab, and only foreign labs are available, often resulting in higher costs and administrative hindrances. Even if the same company offering chemical analysis is operating in several countries, the range of available chemical analysis may differ, and it can be complicated to order a chemical analysis if this analysis is not available on the national market. Additionally, commercial labs that work for industry can have a conflict of interest if they also work for enforcement; The enforcement unit asks industry/companies for existing test results, but then needs to test themselves and use accredited labs and methods that might be the same as industry use.

3.5.2. Online sales and border control

Border control can be a big challenge, as most products have supply chains that involve border transfer. Efficient collaboration with customs authorities was mentioned by one interviewee to be impactful in enforcing compliance. Non-compliant products found in customs face delays, creating financial repercussions for the companies, which can be an efficient tool promoting compliance. This collaboration also leveraged the logistical hurdles of customs to reinforce enforcement measures.

E-shops were mentioned by several interviewees as an increasing challenge to surveil. The number of online stores is large and continues to increase (Eurostat 2023). Furthermore, the rise of online marketplace and e-commerce platforms has created new problems. This is an area of high non-compliance and warrants urgent attention. According to REACH-EN-FORCE REF-8, 78% of tested mixtures or articles sold online fail to meet the requirements of REACH regulations. The actors behind the online stores can be located outside the EEA-area or in other EEA countries. Online stores located outside of the EEA are difficult for national authorities to

control, as the national authorities have no jurisdiction. If the actor behind the online store is located in other EEA states, the case can be transferred to the other EEA state for enforcement.

Trendy toys with short market spans are challenging to quickly identify and supervise, which often requires an adjustment to annual plans. This challenge is further exacerbated when dealing with e-shops and online sales. A similar case occurred during the pandemic when many new players within a short time started to sell disinfectants and protection equipment, without being accustomed to relevant regulations.

As described related to chemical analysis, better availability of information on what chemicals to expect in an article would be beneficial, which is where databases play a role. Product registers, as available in the Nordic countries, were seen as a need in countries lacking that kind of database. Product registers are used to prioritize substances and uses and also to get in direct contact with companies reporting uses of regulated substances. Information on chemical products (mixtures) is very limited in many countries, giving limitations in making risk-based inspections, while this is easier in countries with product registers.

There is no market data available on quantities or how much is imported of different products that could give indications of impact and what would be the most important products to enforce. One database that could serve as a source of information is the database for information on Substances of Concern In articles as such or in complex objects (Products) (SCIP database). But enforcement professionals grapple with limited access to usable information from the SCIP database. Currently, it's not possible to extract data on material categories and which candidate list substances are present in materials, which should be a minimum requirement. Today, the SCIP database gives no mandate for enforcement authorities to extract data beyond that of a regular consumer. Further, there is no function to filter companies with notifications for a certain EEA state, and therefore it is difficult to identify specific companies without SCIP numbers. Critique on the usability of SCIP is also communicated in Romano et al (2023). Better searchability of the SCIP database and right to access data would be an improvement, although SCIP does not show non-compliance with regulations, but candidate list substances for possible future regulations, which is just a small part of what might be relevant to check.

Finding “free riders” (when a person benefits from not paying the costs of compliance work) is another challenge. Tools gathering contact information for companies selling different products would also make enforcement easier.

Some interviewees mentioned current technology as a further strain on the high administrative burden, imposed by EU Commission tools such as Safety Gate and ICSMS. One mentioned ICSMS to have improved a lot, although further development could make it even more user-friendly and create new functionalities.

3.5.3. Resource constraints

In some EEA countries, the absence of enough financial or personnel resources is seen in a lack of good options for running chemical analysis or education on the process from sampling to interpretation of results, or a lack of personnel and resources to perform enough enforcement checks. A lack of resources and diminishing public budgets is juxtaposed with the increasingly complex legislation, requiring heightened knowledge and expertise developed over sustained employment. In several states, it was mentioned that recruiting young professionals was virtually impossible as most young workers with the necessary higher-level education enter the private sector. For those who are recruited, it takes years for inexperienced/young persons to become experts.

Budgets for chemical analysis, including the procurement burden required, were mentioned as a challenge by several of the interviewees. In some countries, it is possible to make the companies pay for tests when non-compliant products are found (national legislation). Still, it would involve an administrative burden. Few interviewees mentioned this option to be used.

3.5.4. Efficient penalties

In many EEA countries there is a lack of legal tools for enforcers to take proper and effective enforcement measures. To demand that companies document and substantiate their compliance poses a challenge to both

enforcement bodies and company entities subject to chemical regulations. Penalties are often difficult to use, except for prohibiting the product from the market, which might be powerful.

If a case is taken to court, often the case goes back to the enforcement body as courts do not prioritize these issues. It could be due to a lack of experience among public prosecutors or that these cases are not seen as a crime or are not a focus for judges. Taking a case to court takes a lot of time and resources, and when the court does not understand the severity of these issues it is not regarded as worthwhile. Jail and financial penalties are very seldom used. For juridical fines, there are constraints on what is seen as reasonable when non-compliant products are found. It is more common to give an administrative fine. One of the interviewees answered that administrative fines are more common in enforcing production at a national level, while only the federal (regional/local?) level uses fines for non-compliant articles/products. A challenge mentioned by one interviewee was given with an example: Cheap jewelry was identified as showing high concentrations of restricted metals (using XRF). Later it was found these articles had not been destroyed but ended up somewhere else, still available on the market. This is especially problematic with e-commerce and articles where the same product can be sold in other web shops. It is hard for enforcers to prove that the shop has the same batch as the one tested by the authority. It could also be that the production or import is found to continue, and that it is difficult to stop it lacking efficient legislative tools.

For chemical products and pesticides, it is easier to check the label and thereby detect non-compliance. As it is costly and causes problems for trade if containers are kept in customs for checking, companies do their best to get compliance certificates before the container comes, which is a good prevention. Charging companies for testing costs in the event of enforcement failure was mentioned as an incentive for compliance. Requiring companies to pay for and send non-compliant products for destruction as hazardous waste, which is expensive and motivates compliance, was also a strategy mentioned. In this case it could be a requirement of a certificate (from the waste company or other independent authority) that the specific product batch was taken away from the market (that the batch was sent back or destroyed), or that destruction could be proved in presence of inspector. Sometimes this was combined with a fee/penalty.

3.5.5. Complex chemicals legislation

The different legislations can also be a challenge. A recycling company can hide behind the Waste directive, as this is a different legislation, that the chemicals enforcement body is not responsible for, and it is not always clear when recycled materials stop being waste and thus how to deal with enforcement. A recycled material can be regarded as a chemical product or an article and it may be difficult to assess the end-of waste status. For POPs, there are clear restrictions on what material has to be destroyed, while this is less clear for other chemical legislations. The scattering of obligations under various EU legislations, for example for Toys-directive RoHS-directive or POP-regulation, makes it complex for companies to understand what to comply with and for enforcers to check, especially if different authorities are responsible for the enforcement of different legislations.

3.6. Future tools to improve enforcement

3.6.1. Digital tools

Multiple digital tools were mentioned as a potential future aid for enforcement. Tailored web crawlers, specialized to meet the specific needs of (enforcement) authorities, are anticipated to enhance information retrieval from the internet. The Commission has developed a new IT application, the eSurveillance – Product Safety, web crawler that detects offers of unsafe products have already been notified in Safety Gate and are still sold or reappear in web shops and online marketplaces. Another tool is under development by the Commission, the Proactive Webcrawler (Terminator of non-compliant products), that revises consumer reviews to detect possible issues with product compliance and safety on products sold online. Notably, Denmark has independently developed an additional crawler tailored for image-based data, further expanding the capabilities of information gathering (*SAFE*).

The integration of AI-driven systems holds promise for automating tasks such as identifying non-compliance on online platforms and drafting administrative letters to communicate non-compliance. Such AI-driven systems would be developed to give data on market information, what products are there and connect the information to a specific economic entity, in what quantities and to extract ICSMS information from it. Harmonization of databases is seen as an important issue, where the specific products should be the unit.

Databases where all companies and the products they are selling are included and with functional filtering opportunities would improve options for prioritizing what to enforce, sample and analyze. For chemical products this is possible, while for articles and complex objects, this may be a bigger challenge, due to the high number of articles and imports and the fact that each batch could be unique. Databases that give a good view of the market, showing what products (in what amounts) are sold at each country's market would help. The next step would be linking this to databases showing non-compliance (Safety Gate), occurrence of candidate list substances (SCIP), and content of materials with high risk of regulated substance content.

Digital product passports, which are on the way to being developed, could be a valuable tool to get information on chemical content, although at the time of interviews, it was not yet clear to what extent this information would be part of the passports, and if all relevant substances will be included. For example, when new SVHCs are added to the candidate list, will these be extractable also retroactively? One of the interviewees said digital product passports are a huge challenge in itself if enforcement bodies will be obliged to check the compliance of information.

Some were very positive to the prospects of digital product passports, if these would give information on chemical content and if this information would be extractable to fit enforcement needs, provided that the data were correct. Observe that control/enforcing the product passport information would be a huge challenge and there is a risk that digital product passports would give an illusion that all products are checked.

Other issues mentioned were: For ICSMS – extraction of information and Adaptable interface from ECHA databases. Digitalization of safety data sheets, that would improve the quality and enforceability of chemical products. A wish for improved information sharing between authorities and EEA states for test results, and the exploration of patent databases for information retrieval, to identify potential risks from chemicals already in the patent phase before reaching the market.

3.6.2. Analytical tools

To improve the enforcement of hazardous chemicals in Europe, various future analytical tools and technologies were envisioned to augment the capabilities of enforcement professionals.

Advanced screening methods are foreseen for substances, particularly in materials like plastics, providing more nuanced insight into the material composition and potential chemical content. Fast, cheap, and hand-held techniques would be a big advantage. For example, XRF can already be used to identify PVC and neoprene, through the content of chlorine, indicating relevant regulated chemicals.

A wish for a general accredited EU Lab that can perform the needed analysis, with standardized and certified analytical methods, was mentioned by several interviewees. According to the Market Surveillance Regulation, the Commission might designate its own testing facilities or public testing facilities of an EEA state as a Union testing facility (EUTF). The EUTF is designated for the purposes of chemical market surveillance to assist the national market surveillance authorities in their activities by contributing to enhancing laboratory capacity where there is a shortage of laboratory testing capacity. The tasks of the EUTFs include testing products and providing technical advice to authorities, among other things.

That analytical methods are developed already when new legislation is adopted was another wish. For example, validated and standardized analytical methods to check compliance with a coming PFAS restriction should be at place before the restriction enters into force.

3.6.3. Financial and personnel resources strengthening chemical enforcement

A critical consideration is the allocation of more resources to enforcement authorities, particularly considering the increasingly complex legislative landscape. This was the only aspect brought up in all 12 interviews. Some commented that the needs are so big that resources would never be enough, so other strategies must be complementary. Often, authorities find themselves with limited staffing resources, frequently comprising just one staff member per legislation, sometimes in the entire EEA state, although normally regional and local level supervision add but depend on resource availability at that level. This inadequacy poses a significant hurdle to effectively navigating intricate regulatory frameworks.

Budgetary provisions for chemical analysis have emerged as a crucial financial tool, enabling authorities to allocate funds systematically. This strategic approach involved earmarking resources for the analysis of specific chemicals, ensuring a targeted and resource-efficient enforcement process. Securing funding for laboratories was thought to ensure the availability of state-of-the-art equipment and skilled personnel, thereby bolstering the overall effectiveness of chemical analysis and enforcement efforts.

3.6.4. Enhancing regulatory measures for effective chemical enforcement

Most professionals interviewed described the ECHA Forum, and learning from other countries, as of utmost importance for chemicals enforcement work. Collaborative efforts among EEA states are facilitated by the use of the ECHA Forum's well-structured projects, promoting a unified approach to enforcement campaigns. Several strategic measures have been suggested to fortify regulatory frameworks and ensure comprehensive compliance.

One is the need for a clearer shift of the burden of proof to companies, a model successfully implemented in Norway. This entails legally empowering enforcement authorities to demand documentation of routines from companies, a mechanism proven to enhance regulatory oversight. This connects to the introduction of a digital product passport system as a transformative tool for improving traceability and verifying product information. The envisioned passport would assign a unique ID number to each product, linking it to the corresponding factory, supplier, and batches. This innovation holds promise for addressing the current challenge of tracing non-compliant articles back to specific batches or production facilities. However, concerns about enforcement mechanisms and surveillance to ensure the accuracy of the product passport highlight the nuanced nature of this proposal.

A novel approach involves linking sanctions to a company's yearly revenue, thereby amplifying the impact of non-compliance. This financial repercussion aims to serve as a deterrent, fostering a more robust adherence to regulatory standards. Sanctions are to be decided upon by each country, as national legislation, and though not an issue for EU regulation.

Efforts to strengthen market surveillance and clarify legislation for handling internet-based sales and repeat offenders have been emphasized. In Denmark, for instance, the possibility of closing the website of an e-store with repetitive non-compliance is a significant regulatory tool. Similar aspirations for stringent enforcement exist in countries like France. Building on successful models from countries such as Denmark and France, there is a proposal to block websites on a national level using the Market Surveillance directive. This initiative seeks to further restrict the import of hazardous substances from outside the EEA, curbing potential sources of non-compliant products. New requirements in the Market Surveillance Regulation (EU (2019/1020)), future requirements in the Digital Services Act ((EU) 2022/2065), General Product Safety Regulation ((EU) 2023/988) and chemical legislations (e.g. CLP regulation) will put pressure on these actors and may contribute to improved legal compliance in the EU. Examples of improvements are traceability of companies and products; improved enforcement tools like closing down webpages, more obligations for marketplaces, and obligations on having an EU representative for non-EU products.

Access to import data has been identified as a crucial tool for faster identification of trend shifts in the market. This proactive approach enables enforcement authorities to stay ahead of emerging challenges and promptly respond to evolving patterns in the importation of chemical substances and products.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

Chemical enforcement related to market surveillance today faces an array of multifaceted challenges that demand innovative solutions and proactive strategies. Rapid technological advancements and the globalized nature of trade introduce new and often uncharted chemical compounds into the market, challenging regulatory bodies to keep pace with evolving risks. The insufficiency of harmonized analytical testing methods at the European level further complicates the enforcement process, leaving authorities reliant on non-standardized approaches. Additionally, inadequate resources, both financial and as personnel, pose constraints on the capacity to conduct rigorous inspections and testing. The increasing prominence of online commerce exacerbates these challenges, as authorities grapple with the vast landscape of e-commerce platforms and the difficulty of regulating products sold across borders.

International collaboration emerged as a key driver to success, with authorities actively engaging in the exchange of best practices. The ECHA Forum plays a key role. Collaboration with customs was seen as another key driver to success, as most non-compliant products enter through import.

The recommended future areas of focus intend to present some activities that are of particularly high value for improving enforcement in the EEA.

The recommended future areas of focus fall within the following categories:

- Development of analytical testing methods
- Development of tools to improve enforcement
- Co-operation and networks within the framework of the ECHA Forum
- Enforcement of online sales and imported products

1. Development of analytical testing methods

One of the important aspects of the enforceability of regulatory measures restricting the use of certain hazardous substances, is the availability of analytical methods that ensure a proper assessment of the presence of restricted substances in products. Harmonized and standardized analytical methods do not exist for all substances under the scope of chemicals legislation. The absence of such methods hampers a harmonized control of conformity of products in the EEA market. Analytical methods benefit market surveillance authorities and customs for their inspection campaigns and assist companies in self-control the products they place on the market.

The EU has moved from a substance-by-substance approach to addressing groups of similar substances in new restrictions. For instance, the restriction proposal on PFAS under REACH covers more than 10 000 different PFAS substances. Enforcement of the restriction for a group of substances presents practical challenges if no testing methods are available. Since millions of products are available at the European market, either manufactured within or entering the EEA from other countries, growing attention is needed for the development of analytical methods that can assess and prove non-compliance with EU legislation more quickly and in a high-throughput manner. Promoting development of cost-effective methods adaptable to a wider range of substances and products is essential. The scientific community plays a significant role in the development of new analytical methods that fit the needs of compliance testing. Recent studies using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) or high-resolution mass spectrometry approaches to characterize the chemical content of products and articles provide promising examples for how advanced analytical methods could be applied in enforcement (Chen et al. 2019; Meng et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2020; Tang 2022). Supporting the regulatory uptake of new analytical techniques is crucial for future progress.

Ideally, analytical methods should be available for all substances before entry into force of the restrictions. The restriction process should be linked with the development of analytical methods. The lack of harmonized and standardized analytical methods is a challenge for enforcement, and ways to improve the situation could be investigated, for example, by cooperation with the standardization bodies such as the European Committee for Standardization (CEN). Standardization of analytical methods used for compliance controls of chemicals is an essential aspect for harmonization and quality results. Through standardization, we may as well promote the development of a competitive market of service providers.

In addition to the development of testing methods, it is important to ensure that there is sufficient laboratory capacity for testing substances in the EEA. To enhance laboratory capacity and ensure consistent testing throughout the EEA, promoting the designation of European Union Testing Facilities (EUTFs) under the Market Surveillance Regulation is recommended where there is a shortage of testing capacity. For example, for textiles there is a lack of independent testing laboratories, laboratory equipment is very expensive, and testing needs to be increased. Textile products are important for the circular economy and capacities should be specifically built up.

It is also important for the market surveillance authorities to have comprehensive information about accredited testing laboratories located within the EEA. Currently, information about laboratories and methods they employ is not gathered in one place, and one option would be to develop a centralized database of laboratories in the EEA.

2. Development of tools to improve enforcement

Enforcement authorities employ various strategies for prioritizing chemical products and articles for enforcement. This includes the utilization of a wide variety of risk-based approaches based on e.g., potential exposure of vulnerable groups (e.g., children) to hazardous substances and information on product or material types of high probability for non-compliance. Defining and practically applying risk-based approaches is important in situations where there is significantly more work to be done than resources available.

As research knowledge increases, perspectives on the prioritization of various risks and the need for regulatory response change. There is a wealth of information available, but compiled, easy to use information for enforcement is not always available. The scientific community could play a more significant role in helping by providing information and tools to help prioritization of products for enforcement. Many activities within the PARC project may also support enforcement. For example, development of analytical test methods, monitoring trends in patent data, information about occurrences of chemicals in products or material types and development of product databases can help enforcement authorities to identify emerging substances and technologies. In addition, exposure data may enable enforcement authorities to prioritize their actions by focusing on substances with the highest potential for harm.

It is important to continue the development of IT tools and AI-based systems for market surveillance at the EEA level. Examples of such tools include web crawlers designed to facilitate the finding of non-compliant products on online shops. It's important also to continue development of already existing tools like ICSMS, which is the common platform used by the market surveillance authorities to inform each other about results and the measures taken in enforcement. Improvement of searchability of the SCIP database and enhanced right to access data by market surveillance authorities would be an improvement. In general, the digitalization of information, such as electronic safety data sheets and digital product passports, along with various databases, can facilitate the better transfer of chemical information within the supply chain.

3. Co-operation and networks within the framework of the ECHA Forum

The ECHA Forum plays a pivotal role in coordinating and harmonizing various EU-wide enforcement activities. It is important to enhance co-operation and networks within the framework of the ECHA Forum. For example, EEA-wide enforcement projects have a significant role in ensuring the compliance of products within the EEA market. At present, Member States finance their participation in projects, including the costs associated with analytical testing. It would be important to explore simple mechanisms for funding opportunities from the European Commission for ECHA projects. If product testing was funded, it could facilitate the participation of Member States in projects and potentially enable the testing of more products.

4. Enforcement of online sales and imported products

Online sales have gained a significant popularity in recent years, particularly during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. With the growth of e-commerce various new types of e-commerce business models have come to the market i.e. marketplaces and dropshipping stores. For market surveillance authorities this poses challenges and requires new ways of enforcement. Enforcement needs to be conducted not only against domestic actors behind but also against actors based in other countries, within or outside EEA. ECHA Forum

projects have shown that online sales are an area of high non-compliance. ECHA Forum has identified this area as a high priority, and the inspections on the next enforcement project focusing on online sales will take place in 2025.

New EU legislation like the Digital Service Act, the Market Surveillance Regulation and the General Product Safety Regulation give new provisions for the e-commerce actors. European cooperation, for example within the framework of the ECHA Forum, is particularly important for learning together how the enforcement of new provisions can be carried out. Where competences are distributed between different authorities in the EEA states there is a need to create structures for national cooperation. It is important to organize awareness campaigns and other ways to increase the level of knowledge regarding the legal obligations when selling products online.

Customs plays a significant role at the EEA borders in ensuring that products entering the EEA market comply with regulations. If the products are inspected before release for free circulation, less enforcement actions are subsequently needed on products already placed in the EEA market. Market surveillance authorities need to continue enhancing the cooperation with customs authorities. ECHA Forum projects have shown high levels of non-compliance in products imported from outside the EEA. In 2024, the ECHA Forum is conducting an enforcement project focusing on imported products, which is being done in cooperation with national customs authorities in the Member States.

Limitations of the study

The authors acknowledge several limitations that may influence the generalization, and applicability of its findings. Notably, the roles and responsibilities of market surveillance authorities vary, with some entities concurrently performing chemical enforcement, while others, such as consumer authorities, may have distinct roles in this regard. Additionally, the close association of chemical enforcement with environmental protection agencies in certain EEA states further introduces variability in the enforcement landscape. These agencies may be engaged in overseeing industry practices related to both chemical usage and emissions to the environment. Moreover, the diversity in the enforcement landscape is exemplified by instances where occupational health and safety enforcement is closely intertwined with chemical enforcement, as observed in certain states. The results of this study may have been expressed differently if others were interviewed, but the interview material was also condensed, and the authors are responsible for the interpretation.

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